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Abstract

The investigation, by advanced physical methods, allows us to identify the chemical composition of volcano stones propelled from the deepness of the globe in various countries on the world and the blue icebergs detached from secular glaciers of Antarctic and Arctic poles.

The stones and ashes of Island contain more elements than those of other volcanos, especially compared to those of Mediterranean countries. This confirms that the earthquake is much important and deeper under eastern Atlantic. Similarly, Sumatra volcano eruptions indicate pronounced tectonics under Western Pacific ocean.

As a primary consequence, the planet temperature increases and induced the melting of thousands years glaciers at the North and South poles, rejecting in the oceans blue icebergs as big as Portugal or Vietnam. Nevertheless the sea level rising is not a great danger compared to its local sudden elevations, tsunamis, which cause tremendous damages.

I have calculated the areas immerged by tsunamis, applied in particular for the deltas of North and South Vietnam, Indonesia; Malaysia and some European countries.

The results will be presented in hope to prevent sudden damages and in long term, the effects on lands, environments and on the health of humanity.

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Introduction

The continental plate's tectonics provokes volcano eruptions which contribute mainly to the warming of the planet. The recent very important eruptions appear at sites different than the previous ones, on global surfaces as well as under the oceans and the earthquakes, especially near the littorals often cause sudden sea level risings named tsunamis and induce strong damages : land immerging, erosion, population evacuation, destruction of housing buildings... even nuclear plants when they are located near the littoral transforming "pacific centrals" into nuclear bombs in retardement.

The author will give the results of his analytical measurements with modern physical techniques such as MicroRaman Spectroscopy, X-ray Fluorescence Spectroscopy through Electron Microscope etc... These methods have been used with efficiency for various advanced materials and nano-materials.

Results and Discussion

From many expeditions in Iceland, Norway and South poles Antarctic region, I have collected and studied blue icebergs detached from glaciers and solid volcanic rocks and ashes projected at recent eruptions, in comparison to those I recorded from several sites of continental Europe and La Soufriere, Reunion.

Table 1.

SPECTRO X-LAB			Job Number: 2014	
Preset Sample Data				
Sample Name:	ISLANDERS	Dilution Material:	None	
Description:		Sample Mass (g):	0.5000	
Method:	Tq-33892	DilutionMass(g)	0.0000	
Job Number:	2014	Dilution Factor:	1.0000	
Sample State	Pressed tablet, 32 mm	Sample rotation:	No	
Sample Type	Pressed tablet	Date of Receipt:	09/08/2014	
Sample Status	AAAXXX	Date of Evaluation:	09/08/2014	
Results				
The error is the statistical error with 1 sigma confidence interval				
			Loss of Ignition:	72.3980 %
Z	Symbol	Element	Concentration	Abs.Error
11	Na ₂ O		< 0.76 %	(0.0) %
12	MgO		< 0.11 %	(0.0) %
13	Al ₂ O ₃		5.693 %	0.08 %
14	SiO ₂		20.93 %	0.06 %
15	P ₂ O ₅		0.4186 %	0.0096 %
16	SO ₃		1.021 %	0.007 %
17	Cl	Chlorine	0.1207 %	0.0008 %
19	K ₂ O		0.6068 %	0.0088 %
20	CaO		6.925 %	0.025 %
22	TiO ₂		2.007 %	0.011 %
23	V ₂ O ₅		0.0326 %	0.0064 %
24	Cr ₂ O ₃		0.0343 %	0.0034 %
25	MnO		0.1099 %	0.0031 %
26	Fe ₂ O ₃		10.26 %	0.03 %
27	CoO		0.0286 %	0.0033 %
28	NiO		0.00453 %	0.00062 %
29	CuO		0.00869 %	0.00046 %
30	ZnO		0.05614 %	0.00080 %
31	Ga	Gallium	0.00027 %	0.00010 %
32	Ge	Germanium	< 0.00022 %	(0.0) %
33	As ₂ O ₃		0.00112 %	0.00028 %
34	Se	Selenium	< 0.00011 %	(0.0) %
35	Br	Bromine	0.00055 %	0.00007 %
37	Rb ₂ O		0.00155 %	0.00010 %
38	SrO		0.01947 %	0.00027 %
39	Y	Yttrium	0.00256 %	0.00013 %
40	ZrO ₂		< 0.068 %	(0.0) %
41	Nb ₂ O ₅		< 0.0034 %	(0.0028) %
42	Mo	Molybdenum	0.01293 %	0.00079 %
47	Ag	Silver	< 0.0016 %	(0.0) %
48	Cd	Cadmium	< 0.0022 %	(0.0) %
49	In	Indium	< 0.0018 %	(0.0) %
50	SnO ₂		< 0.0039 %	(0.0) %
51	Sb	Antimony	< 0.0040 %	(0.0) %
52	Te	Tellurium	< 0.0060 %	(0.0) %
53	I	Iodine	< 0.0093 %	(0.0025) %
55	Cs	Cesium	0.0121 %	0.0054 %
56	BaO	Barium	< 0.025 %	(0.014) %
57	La	Lathanum	< 0.039 %	(0.031) %
58	Ce	Cerium	< 0.0100 %	(0.0092) %

Table 2. Volcano Vesuve.

Element Series	unn. C [wt.%]	norm. C [wt.%]	Atom. C [at.%]
Oxygen K-series	45.76	46.1	63.1
Silicon K-series	19.64	19.79	15.43
Zirconium L-series	0.7	0.71	0.17
Aluminium K-series	9.28	9.35	7.59
Calcium K-series	8.56	8.62	4.71
Iron K-series	5.82	5.86	2.3
Sodium K-series	3.1	3.12	2.97
Potassium K-series	1.89	1.9	1.07
Magnesium K-series	2.18	2.19	1.97
Titanium K-series	0.86	0.86	0.39
Copper K-series	0.28	0.28	0.1
Sulfur K-series	0.03	0.03	0.02
Gold L-series	1.09	1.1	0.12
Chlorine K-series	0.08	0.08	0.05
Total:	99.27	100	100

and for Northern and Southern Deltas of Vietnam.

Saigon today

Saigon ngâ.p 2 mét

Saigon under 4 meters

The destruction of the nuclear plant in North Japan on 2011 resulted from the above process ! After this catastrophe, all the nuclear plants have been arrested for non function. But last month, the Sendai reactor is started again in service ! What a big danger!

Please stop all nuclear plants, before they become un-voluntary nuclear bombs. No body and no responsible organization must argue the need of national energy and neglect the well-being and the massive dead of humanity.

Hanoi today

Hanoi ngâ.p 2 met

Hanoi under 4 meters

Glaciers Melting

Glaciers have been formed very longtime ago all over the world, especially at Arctic and Antarctic, and their melting has been very slow during centuries. Their blue color attests, by optical refraction property, that they are compressed by the weight of successive snow layers. Although their density is higher than that of glass, but continues to be lighter than that of sea water at 4°C near the North and South Poles. The glaciers are in contact with soil bed and move slowly towards the sea. The frontal part of them named *glacier tongue* or shelf, is floating on the sea surface. I have assisted many times to their cracks provoking tremendous noisy falls of detached glaciers.

This year, nearly at the same time of important volcanic eruptions at the two globe hemispheres, hot waters appeared under the tongues at Antarctica and induced the ***collapse of glaciers at a rate much more frequent than never before***. In consequence, big blue icebergs are melting and *moving towards the Equator* because the centrifugal forces generated by the rotation of the globe. Therefore, the elevation of sea level will accelerate, more than 1 cm recorded after two last decades of observation. Of course, *the areas from -20 and +20 parallels will assist to the highest sea rising*. In addition, as the immerging volume of the icebergs is nearly ten times that of their apparent part, and the moving glaciers melt water is not in the same place than the initial glaciers ***we must observe a change of the rotation axis of the world, inducing new immerged lands and new emerged lands***.

I do think that the volcanic eruptions and continental plate's tectonics and dynamics under the sea are the main causes of the warming and climate change in Antarctic region.

Conclusion

The global warming continues to increase. In the greenhouse effect, it is a fault to only consider Carbon dioxide because the contribution of Water vapor is thousand times more important. Therefore Carbon tax must be substituted by WVTax due to its strong green effect. All polluters and combustible furnisners must pay. The volcanic warming must be principally taken into account. The plate tectonics can violently appear at new sites and cause big tsunamis with damaging effects. Finally, the glaciers melting

in more accelerated rate will contribute to the elevation of the sea level and the change of the geography of the world, even a change of the rotation axis of the globe.

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